

Deliverable D1.2 – AtlantECO Environmental Sustainability

Dissemination level: Public

Related Work Package	WP1 Coordination and Cooperation
Related task(s)	Task 1.5
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Due date	28.02.2022
Submission date	30.03.2022
Type	Report
Status and version	Final V1.00

Declaration: Any work or result described therein is a genuine output of the AtlantECO project. Any other source will be properly referenced where and when relevant.

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1 Version History

Version	Authors	Summary of changes	Date
0.1	E. Trabut	Initial draft	13.09.2021
0.2	E. Trabut	Adding content	22.02.2022
1.0	E. Trabut	Finalising content	30.03.2022

2 Executive summary

The purpose of the deliverable is to establish a strategy for Environmental Sustainability in AtlantECO as we define the processes and structures in place to support its delivery and measure its implementation. This deliverable is describing the expected collective policies, actions and behaviours to ensure responsibility of the consortium towards limiting environmental impact whilst carrying out the activities of the AtlantECO project.

The document will cover:

- Brief introduction
- The principles followed to identify Environmental Sustainability activities in AtlantECO
- The principles to be adopted for the selected activities
- A strategy roadmap for developing and implementing policies and common practices as well as the framework needed to evaluate the impact and ensure lessons learnt are captured as legacy of the project efforts.

This document is set up as the first step in addressing the environmental challenges of the research activities and will be followed by the full roadmap, sets of policies and common practices, as well as a portfolio of tools and resources developed and updated as and when needed during the project. End of project measures and metrics of implementation and impact will be included in the final report of the project.

This document is based on the terms and conditions established in the Grant Agreement (GA) and its Annexes, as well as in the Consortium Agreement (CA).

3 Introduction

The AtlantECO Project aims to study the Atlantic Ocean from pole to pole to determine the structure and function of the Atlantic microbiome in the context of ocean circulation and presence of pollutants to assess 1) its role in driving the dynamics of Atlantic ecosystems at basin and regional scales; 2) its potential of being used as a sensor of ecosystem state and 3) the mechanism by which it drives the provision of ecosystem services.

In order to deliver this, the project builds on four activity streams (AS)

- **AS1: Asses the status of the ecosystem structures, functions, health and services** at regional, basin and all Atlantic scales and provide high quality gridded data products and maps
- **AS2: Enhance knowledge and innovate** by adopting standard optical and genetic observations protocols, cutting-edge network analysis methods and better parametrisation of connectivity and biogeochemical models
- **AS3: Assess drivers and stressors of change and forecast** their impact on tipping points and recovery of ecosystem structures, functions and services and develop eco-socio-economic models to predict their future states
- **AS4: Share and use** capacity and knowledge across the four continents bordering the Atlantic Ocean ensuring a seamless engagement between science, industry, policy and society.

AtlantECO addresses three major challenges **microbiome, plastics and the plastisphere** and **seascape and connectivity** and defines these as the scientific concepts underpinning the Project which, together with their interactions, will help address the gap in current knowledge and understanding on how they affect ecology, biodiversity, sensitivity to climate change and the potential for a sustainable exploitation of Atlantic natural resources. Building on the knowledge acquired about the status and dynamics of the Atlantic ecosystem, an additional challenge will be to optimize a set of tools and metrics to tightly couple ecosystem functioning and socio-economic activities, integrating them in a unified framework with Eco-Socio-Economic analyses and projections, which we consider a prerequisite for the sustainable management of the Atlantic Ocean. A final challenge to be addressed by AtlantECO is the design of a strategy and of procedures to guarantee that the new unified framework will be implemented in a systemic way so that all the components of the implicated societies in countries bordering the basin will contribute to the implementation and will fully benefit from it.

AtlantECO focuses on five ecosystem services:

- **ES1:** Climate support system: carbon drawdown and storage
- **ES2:** Deep Ocean life support system: transfer of matter & energy to mesopelagic and seabed ecosystems.
- **ES3:** Food security and the trophic fluxes: fisheries and aquaculture.
- **ES4:** Healthy planet, healthy people: biohazards, cycling of plastics and pollutants
- **ES5:** Biodiversity: resilience, adaptation and contribution to the Bioeconomy, including new chemicals

Within this Framework, AtlantECO pledges to identify and implement a set of guiding principles and practices to limit the carbon footprint of its activities. To do so we build on existing tools, framework and recommendations that have been published and adapt them to the AtlantECO specific activities.

The document sets out to establish key principles and a roadmap to update, implement and monitor these as practices for the project activities for the remaining implementation phase of the project.

The action plan and timeline for implementing the strategy are then outlined in conclusion of the report.

4 Principles of Environmental Sustainability in AtlantECO

4.1 What are we trying to achieve?

To make the project as environmentally friendly as possible, i.e. limit the environmental footprint of the activities essential to the delivery of AtlantECO's objectives and expected impact.

Whilst it is impossible to achieve a no environmental impact status whilst carrying out the activities of the project, it is important to identify and understand where and how much we impact the environment as well as where we can limit this impact. We keep in mind that, from a cost/benefit perspective, we believe that the outcome of the project will bring long-term benefits to environmental management which will outweigh the punctual costs in terms of ecological impact/footprint.

4.2 Where do we start, what do we need to know?

To define the most relevant aspects of environmental sustainability for the AtlantECO project and its activities, we apply the “Ten simple rules to make your research more sustainable”¹ (Figure 1), we will then follow with examples of actions and behaviours which can reduce the impact of the project activities in the next sections.

Figure 1: 10 rules to make your research more sustainable, adapted for AtlantECO

4.2.1 RULE 1: Cherry picking

It is important to understand that we cannot address all aspects and all levels of the project activities, but that selected actions, wherever and whenever we can, will add up to make a difference, and will be a basis to build upon in time.

¹ Ligozat, A. L., Névéol, A., Daly, B., & Frenoux, E. (2020). Ten simple rules to make your research more sustainable. *PLoS Computational Biology*, 16(9), e1008148. <https://journals.plos.org/ploscompbiol/article?id=10.1371/journal.pcbi.1008148>

Here, we focalise on the specific activities of the AtlantECO project (macro level) and less on the usual day to day operations of the beneficiaries involved in the project (micro level). These are obviously important aspects to consider but there is limited time and resources available within AtlantECO to 1) identify, 2) quantify, 3) adopt changes and 4) measure the impact of changes at the level of each organisation. This is the rationale for the focus on project specific activities, which are defined as activities that would not have happened if AtlantECO didn't exist. These are identified under rule 2 below.

4.2.2 RULE 2: Be informed

It is important to understand which activities are specifically energivore in AtlantECO when looking at carbon footprint to be able to develop guiding principles that make the most sense.

The aspects we will focus on include:

- Transportation
- Field research
- Meetings
- Digital Technology
- Project promotion and dissemination material

4.2.3 RULE 3: Prefer train over plane

It is a well-known fact that international air travel contributes to a major extent towards carbon emissions in many activities.

The AtlantECO consortium spans three continents, and land transportation cannot be used in all circumstances. There are essential travels for the realisation of the project's objectives in line with the tasks to be delivered, for example transportation of scientists, crew members and material/equipment deployed for sampling expeditions. Furthermore, air-transportation of samples towards the biobanking and sequencing facilities is necessary. Without this, the tasks cannot be delivered.

In addition to essential travels, there are other instances where air travel is difficult to avoid, for example the attendance at General Assembly meetings to which all beneficiaries are expected to participate. Whilst remote events, or hybrid events are becoming more and more prevalent, and should be the preferred means of delivery, there are many positive aspects of maintaining a minimum of face-to-face meetings to optimise the collaborations and decision-making mechanisms, as well as to support the establishment of networks, especially for the earlier career researchers.

4.2.4 RULE 4: Take advantage of remote participation

Due to the pandemic situation over the last two years, and the restrictions imposed on travels, the solutions for remote working and meetings have developed exponentially. This has already been experienced by the AtlantECO consortium for whom most meetings have taken place online.

The benefit seen in terms of reduced environment footprint of events, compared to previous in-person events, organised remotely during 2020 and 2021, is undeniable², it is therefore important to ensure that the lessons learned from the possibilities of remote participation can be integrated into common practices going forward.

In addition, virtual meetings can support more widespread attendance, enabling the participation of people who might not be able to if the meeting is in person only. This means more team members can benefit from the events, especially junior team members such as MSc or PhD students and those who could not be absent from their home for long periods of time, for example parents or people caring for family members.

² Greening the blue report 2021, UN environment programme, accessed: <https://wedocs.unep.org/bitstream/handle/20.500.11822/37330/GB21.pdf>

Going a step further, there is a push for stricter requirements for research activities to be done in line with least carbon emission, including the systematic delivery of dissemination events as virtual, keeping those that require international travelling for objectives such as career development, capacity building and international exchange of staff³, as well as ensuring access to infrastructure and maximising research efforts.

4.2.5 RULE 5: Work collectively and reproducibly

The idea behind the rule is to use and share the processes and methods already in place and proven to work to avoid duplication of effort. This specifically for the research activities directly, this includes methods, protocols and codes for example.

In AtlantECO, it is implemented by design as there is an objective to develop and deploy common standard protocols across organisations around the Atlantic basin, by beneficiary organisations and third parties alike. While this makes obvious methodological sense when applied to the activities of a common project, it is important to note that the standards developed are made available to everyone during and after the lifetime of the project, meaning that the sustainability of the approach can be built on over time.

4.2.6 RULE 6: Encourage bottom-up sustainable initiatives

Individuals' behaviours and actions contribute to changing the bigger picture, each should be aware and question their daily habits and practices to select the most relevant options for least environmental impact while still achieving the objectives of the project as a whole. In addition, it is crucial to build on current practices and examples of successful initiatives already in place at individual and institutional levels and which could be transferred to other settings, and it is therefore primordial to have open discussions on these issues at the consortium level.

The AtlantECO consortium brings together many partners from all around the Atlantic basin which means that there are many differences to be considered when developing policies and common practices. Differences can be seen in the infrastructures, cultures, access to resources, transportation options, bureaucracy, etc. Therefore, it might not be feasible to implement the same practices across all 36 organisations and local adaptations are to be expected. This is where a bottom-up approach and co-design method is important in defining the policies and practices that will be adopted so that local challenges and opportunities are both integrated.

Combining the bottom-up approach and tailoring to the local context for implementation will help optimise the chances of buy-in, roll out and success for the policies and practices.

4.2.7 RULE 7: Evaluate the impact of your research practices

In order to understand where changes can be made it is important to have an idea of what impact is made by the research activities themselves, rather than the environment or the context within which these are conducted. These include the direct impact, for example by knowing how the choice of a method over another can change the impact made, or how the research activity could be affecting biodiversity; and the indirect impact, meaning the aftermath of the research activities, how the results are used and knowing if this improves the environmental conditions or if it leads to less harm done to the ecosystems.

AtlantECO aims to gain a better understanding of the Atlantic Ecosystems so that we can better manage the ocean, its biodiversity and the chain of services that depend on these ecosystems. However, do we know how

³ Bousema, T., Burtscher, L., van Rij, R. P., Barret, D., & Whitfield, K. (2022). The critical role of funders in shrinking the carbon footprint of research. *The Lancet Planetary Health*, 6(1), e4-e6. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2542-5196\(21\)00276-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2542-5196(21)00276-X)

the research activities affect the environment it is studying? What are the trade-offs and where can we make better choices?

Some AtlantECO research activities will have considerable energy consumption and carbon emissions associated to them, for example sea expeditions, all the activities linked to the vast amount of data used and produced, its storage, curation, sharing and use in numerical models all require computational power and an IT infrastructure that is hungry in energy. But the outcomes of the project will lead to better models and tools to be used for a more sustainable management of the Atlantic ocean's resources and improve its health.

These are aspects to be considered during the development of policies and practices.

4.2.8 RULE 8: Ask sustainability research questions

The purpose of this document and the process that will follow is to do exactly this, ask the sustainability questions on the research that we conduct in AtlantECO. And while some aspects were considered during the preparation of the project, including the dedication of a task in the coordination WP and this deliverable, most of the work remains to be done to actually understand the sustainable components of the research and the actions that can contribute to limit environmental damage during the project, and in the long term, via indirect impact but also by sharing this knowledge with the wider research community, in the marine sciences and beyond.

4.2.9 RULE 9: Transfer eco-friendly gestures from home to the lab

In line with rule 6, building on the gestures and habits from individuals to their labs, and for the purpose of this exercise, also from their organisation to the consortium wide activities is a key approach to optimising the chances of success for the policies and practices we will develop. Using existing solutions that have been tried and tested in other places is another way to ensure there is no duplication of effort, or at least that those existing solutions are optimised if they need to be.

4.2.10 RULE 10: Raise awareness

Raising awareness, sharing knowledge and educating people on the challenges and necessities to tackle environmental sustainability is key to support changes and incite action. The more relevant the information can be regarding the specific impact, challenges and solutions of the activities we are addressing, the more relatable it will be for all involved. The more information and knowledge we can gain and share about the impact of AtlantECO activities on the environment, the more we can make informed decisions about our individual and collective actions.

Therefore, awareness raising, and literacy components will be fully integrated in the roadmap and follow up activities linked with environmental sustainability in AtlantECO as defined in section 5 of this deliverable. They will build onto existing material and be adapted to different levels of specificity (e.g. 1) collaborative research, 2) marine research and 3) AtlantECO activities) where and when possible.

As part of awareness raising, we will include what the environmental impact/footprint of scientific research is compared to global trade and tourism, for example, as well as acknowledge the huge benefits brought by scientific advances and technological innovations to our culture and the future management of our planet.

4.3 What can we actually do?

4.3.1 The AtlantECO aspects selected

As seen in rule 2, we will be focusing on five aspects of the project activities to act on (Figure 2)

Figure 2: the AtlantECO activities targeted for improving practices for carbon impact reduction

For each of these categories, we look at the carbon footprint and some existing recommendations⁴ and tools⁵ to develop guiding principles which will be used to define policies and common practices.

4.3.2 Transport

Figure 3 Carbon footprint of travel per passenger kilometre, downloaded from our world in data: <https://ourworldindata.org/travel-carbon-footprint>

Considering all research activities, the carbon emissions linked to international air travel is the greatest contributor⁶ and has been identified as a key aspect to address when looking at reducing the environmental impact of research. These aspects were covered in rules 3 above and to address them the following principles are defined:

⁴ Set of policy briefs and guidelines published by Climate-friendly Climate Research, a JPI initiative. Accessed: <http://www.jpi-climate.eu/jpi-strategy/climatefriendlyclimateresearch>

⁵ Greening the blue tutorial, accessed: <https://www.greeningtheblue.org/tutorial>

⁶ Barret, D. Estimating, monitoring and minimizing the travel footprint associated with the development of the Athena X-ray Integral Field Unit. *Exp Astron* 49, 183–216 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10686-020-09659-8>

Transport Principle 1: Limit air travel to events where in person attendance is required to achieve the objectives of the event in line with the objectives of the AtlantECO project.

Transport Principle 2: Offset emissions in case air travel or another major carbon emissions source cannot be avoided in terms of a reasonable alternative using existing (international) train connections or other climate-friendly alternatives.

Transport Principle 3: Favour travelling for the younger/earlier career scientists of the project who are in greater need to develop and establish their networks.

Transport Principle 4: Combine reasons to travel with multiple events to be attended in a single or nearby location.

4.3.3 Field work

The use of research, commercial and citizens' vessels contributing to the AtlantECO sampling programme will certainly count for a large part of the carbon footprint of the project. Within the transport sector, which accounts for 16.2% of the global greenhouse gas emissions, shipping is the third contributor, with 1,7% of total emissions behind road and aviation⁷.

Source: EMSA/EEA (2021).

Figure 4 Pollutant emissions to the atmosphere and water body from a generic ship, source: European Maritime Transport Environmental Report 2021⁸

AtlantECO uses sailing boats for flagship and project specific sampling, in addition protocols are used on board of research and third-party expeditions that are already taking place and therefore limiting project specific carbon emissions, in line with recommendations made towards reducing emissions in marine research⁹. The

⁷ Ritchie, H (2018). Sector by sector: where do global greenhouse gas emissions come from? *Our world in data*. Accessed: <https://ourworldindata.org/ghg-emissions-by-sector>

⁸ European Maritime Transport Environmental Report 2021. Accessed: https://www.euneighbours.eu/sites/default/files/publications/2021-09/EMTER_Report_TH-AL-21-004-EN-N.pdf

⁹ W R Turrell, Marine science within a net-zero emission statutory framework, *ICES Journal of Marine Science*, Volume 76, Issue 7, December 2019, Pages 1983–1993, <https://doi.org/10.1093/icesjms/fsz164>

sampling activities on board of third-party cruises and citizen's vessels are part of an existing cruise that would have taken place with or without the existence of AtlantECO, these are therefore an indirect contribution to our environmental footprint.

There are however 2 cruises with AtlantECO dedicated sampling activities, i.e. expeditions or parts of expeditions would not have taken place if AtlantECO didn't exist.

Field work Principle 1: Optimise emissions of the operating platform and the management of resources on board.

Field work Principle 2: Stop pollution of the ocean with technological equipment (e.g. drifters, floats) that is not recuperated post use.

4.3.4 Meetings

Figure 5: Aspects of face-to-face events which most contribute to its carbon footprint, based on multiple sources.

As mentioned earlier, the travel aspects of meetings account for the largest contribution to its footprint and this is irrespective of whether it requires international transport or is a regional attendance meeting. In AtlantECO, to limit the need to travel and/or the number of people needed to travel by air, we establish the following principles:

Meetings Principle 1: Where possible, substitute in-person meetings with virtual meetings using video-/ tele-conferencing technologies. In addition, all events should have remote participation as an option.

Meetings Principle 2: when organising face to face events, plan multiple events at the same time in the same place to optimise use of time on site and increase impact of events.

Meetings Principle 3: Implement a regional hub approach, for which each hub is reachable by land transport

Not only will virtual meetings limit travel requirements but also, it has been shown that as well as having a substantially reduced carbon footprint (by up to 94%), virtual meetings are less expensive to organise and deliver⁶. It is also noted that delivery of hybrid events, where both in person and remote attendance as proposed, the carbon footprint can be 67% lower than fully in person events¹⁰, when a hub approach is used.

¹⁰ ao, Y., Steckel, D., Klemeš, J.J. et al. Trend towards virtual and hybrid conferences may be an effective climate change mitigation strategy. Nat Commun 12, 7324 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-021-27251-2>

In addition to limiting the number of face-to-face meetings to reduce associated environmental footprint altogether; when in person events are organised, we will apply a green event planning and implementation approach to reduce our environmental impacts in the aspects illustrated in Figure 5.

Many recommendations exist on how to organise and deliver green events¹¹, AtlantECO will build on these existing resources to develop its policy and common practices for events and meetings. For example, we have linked with the organisers of the ICES conference which has been working towards a reduction of its carbon footprint for many years, and the collaboration will be crucial to utilising proven approaches and avoiding unnecessary efforts to define new solutions.

Meetings Principle 4: when organising in person events, apply principles for responsible and sustainable events

4.3.5 Digital technologies

Figure 6 Carbon emissions from global ICT. Source: Belkhir & Elmeligi, 2018¹²

Infrastructure, within which emissions linked to Information Communication technology (ICT) are considered, can account for a considerable amount of environmental footprint in research¹³ and this is set to grow rapidly over time if attitudes and actions don't change¹². It therefore makes it an important aspect to address when thinking of reducing environmental impact.

While taking into account the full spectrum of Digital Technology (DT) related emissions linked to the AtlantECO specific activities is impossible, a few items that are isolated from the intra-muros contributions of each organisation can be considered. These include: the project website, the project repository, the web-conferencing account and its utilisation and the use of emails in project-specific communications.

¹¹ Leochico, C. F. D., Di Giusto, M. L., & Mitre, R. (2021). Impact of scientific conferences on climate change and how to make them eco-friendly and inclusive: A scoping review. *The Journal of Climate Change and Health*, 4, 100042.

¹² Belkhir, L., & Elmeligi, A. (2018). Assessing ICT global emissions footprint: Trends to 2040 & recommendations. *Journal of cleaner production*, 177, 448-463.

¹³ Achten, WMJ & Almeida, Joana & Muys, Bart. (2013). Carbon footprint of science: More than flying. *Ecological Indicators*. 34. 352-355. 10.1016/j.ecolind.2013.05.025.

The following estimated CO₂ equivalents can be considered when looking at individual impact:

Figure 7 Estimated CO₂ equivalent emissions of individual use of a computer and its usage. Source: Berners-Lee, 2010¹⁴

For the selected areas of DT use in AtlantECO-specific activities we define the following principles

Tools exist for achieving an environmental digital sustainability, defined as “**Environment-centered design is an approach to product or service development that aims to make products or services environmentally, socially and economically sustainable by focusing on the needs, limitations and preferences of target human audience and non-human strategic stakeholders. It involves knowledge and design techniques developed at the intersection of human-centered design, usability, ecology, and sustainability science**”¹⁵ (Sznal, 2020)

Approaches includes reducing video sizes before making them available online¹⁶, or by taking a sustainable web design approach¹⁷

DT Principle 1: Implement an Environmental Digital Sustainability approach on all our online platforms for the full Virtual Life Cycle.

Digital sobriety approaches can also be implemented in the communication resources and tools used by AtlantECO, such as emailing (e.g. links rather than attachments, fewer emails with multiple information, no printing of emails) and tele-/web-conferencing (e.g. sending background material prior to meetings, keeping audio only and limiting screen sharing). For each it will be important to understand how we are able to limit the carbon footprint to the minimum possible while achieving the expected objectives and maintaining a coherent collaboration.

DT Principle 2: Practice digital sobriety and minimalist approach in project communication and dissemination.

¹⁴ MLA. Berners-Lee, Mike. *How Bad Are Bananas?: the Carbon Footprint of Everything*. London :Profile, 2010.

¹⁵ Sznal M., 2020. The time for Environment-Centered Design has come. Uxdesign. Accessed: <https://uxdesign.cc/the-time-for-environment-centered-design-has-come-770123c8cc61>

¹⁶ The Shift Project, 2019. *How can I reduce the size of a video in 5 minutes while maintaining a good quality?* Accessed: https://theshiftproject.org/wp-content/uploads/2019/09/Guide-Reducing-the-weight-of-your-videos-in-5-minutes_V6.pdf

¹⁷ Frick, T. 2022. Sustainable Web Design, Mightybytes. Accessed: <https://www.mightybytes.com/blog/sustainable-web-design/>

4.3.6 Products: communication, outreach, and dissemination material

“Of course, if we go for digital information without ditching the paper, downloading stuff simply to print it out, we end up with the worst of all carbon worlds.”

Mike Berners-Lee¹⁸

For this category it is important to integrating the concepts of sustainable procurement, as defined by the UN system as “*practices that integrate requirements, specifications and criteria that are compatible and in favour of the protection of the environment, of social progress and is support of economic development, namely by seeking resource efficiency, improving the quality of products and services and ultimately optimising costs*”, with considerations of the full life cycle of any product, digital or physical, that is to say from supply chain to disposal.

AtlantECO has limited production of material, digital or physical, and the contribution to its environmental impact will be minimal, however sustainability in procuring and producing goods and digital material goes beyond the Carbon footprint to encompass broader societal challenges. Therefore, this is addressed to ensure a global sustainability value alignment in the way we select, procure, use and dispose of any material coming out of AtlantECO.

Recommendations and performance indicators exist to address the full life cycle considerations to be made^{19,20}, these will be used when developing the policies and common practices in the next steps of our sustainability process.

Products Principle 1: Consider the sustainability aspects of the full life cycle of materials and products, from the start of the supply chain to the disposal/re-entry into cycle stages.

¹⁸ Berners-Lee, M. (2020). *How bad are bananas?: the carbon footprint of everything*. Profile Books.

¹⁹ Sustainability the missing link, The Economist intelligence Unit, 2018. Accessed: https://impact.econ-asia.com/perspectives/sites/default/files/llamasoft_report_-_report_digital_2_2_0.pdf

²⁰ Accessed: <https://www.ungm.org/Shared/KnowledgeCenter/Pages/SustainableProcurementIndicatorProject>

5 Roadmap for implementation and measuring

The following section establishes a roadmap for implementing the principles identified above as practices in the project. The practices will be discussed and agreed with all partners in the project to ensure co-design and buy-in from the start. When possible, we will engage with experts to support us in the development, implementation and evaluation of the strategy since this is a complex issue for which specialist knowledge and experience is required. Lessons learnt, case studies and recommendations will be drawn from the AtlantECO experience to share and help improve future eco-friendly research approaches. The roadmap structure follows the process outlined in Figure 3

Figure 8: Overview of roadmap for developing, implementing, measuring and improving the impact of policies and common practices supporting eco-friendly research in AtlantECO.

5.1 Guiding: Policies & practices

In order to turn the principles defined above into actionable practices, we will develop a set of project policies and common practices that will be co-designed, taking a bottom-up approach to ensure that the solutions put forward are realistic and feasible in practice and within the context they are destined to be implemented in.

Co-design will be done with volunteering individuals from the consortium and in consultation with partners before policies and common practices are adopted.

Policies will define the scope covered, the actions to be implemented, the Key Performance indicators to be measured and the tools and resources to do so. Wherever possible we will call on external contributors and experts to help design the policies based on successful initiatives that already exist.

5.2 Enabling: awareness and knowledge exchange

To optimise the implementation of policies and common practices it will be crucial to provide tools, resources and knowledge to all in AtlantECO. As such a programme of training and communication will be developed to cover the aspects and activities selected. Background information, Carbon literacy, infographics, useful tips and visual guide versions of the policies will be developed and made available to all. A dedicated page will be added to the AtlantECO website for public access, with informative and actionable material to raise awareness on the responsibility of singular citizens in e.g. reducing waste going to the ocean, acidification, biodiversity loss, climate change and air pollution.

Special awareness campaigns for AtlantECO members and the public, could be implemented based on the example of the one-UN quiz organised at the occasion of World Environment Day.

Selected from the “Green the blue” report as being most adapted to the focus of AtlantECO principles, training could be delivered on general environmental behaviour, sustainable procurement, sustainable events, Sustainable/Green ICT and biodiversity conservation.

5.3 Implementing: facilitate and roll out

To ensure the success of the strategy, it is crucial to establish an overall culture and mindset established from individual to consortium to develop and maintain habits and actions towards a more sustainable approach in all AtlantECO activities, and more than likely beyond, by repercussions.

Addressing environmental sustainability is challenging, even more so when the initiatives target activities with a relatively short lifetime within a temporary collaboration. The scale of policies and practices, and the schedule to implement them, must therefore align to these conditions so that we are able to sustain them during the project, and to avoid overpromising and underdelivering on all of these.

Clear and efficient plans for implementation will therefore need to be developed for each policy/common practice adopted, including well-defined responsibilities and schedules.

5.4 Evaluating: how to measure impact?

To understand the efficiency and success of the approach, it will be important to measure the impact made. This is a complex issue and usually requires a lot of time and resources. Therefore, we will need to develop a realistic and efficient framework to record and measure the impact of the policies and practices, and to do so without having to add too much work on top of AtlantECO’s research activities. Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) will be defined and included at the policy/common practice design phase, and this step of the process will define how to measure and report on these KPIs. For the activities preceding the implementation of the policies/practices a more qualitative approach may need to be undertaken.

5.5 Improving: sharing for legacy

To help ensure the activities and initiatives developed, implemented, and measured during AtlantECO can support future initiatives, a process to capture feedback, lessons learnt and case studies to celebrate success and provide concrete examples of what can be done will be available. These will be collected and published on the website and permanent repository Zenodo as well integrated as a chapter into the roadmap for future activities (deliverable D10.5) produced at the end of the project.

6 Conclusion

“We must [also] be at the forefront of showing how to reduce emissions, developing the technology and strategies to reduce our own emissions while pursuing our profession and hence, most importantly, leading by example”

W.R. Turrell⁹

6.1 Summary of the principles

Transport Principle 1: Limit air travel to events where in person attendance is required to achieve the objectives of the event in line with the objectives of the AtlantECO project.

Transport Principle 2: Offset emissions in case air travel or another major carbon emissions source cannot be avoided in terms of a reasonable alternative using existing (international) train connections or other climate-friendly alternatives.

Transport Principle 3: Favour traveling for the younger/earlier career scientists of the project who are in greater need to develop and establish their networks.

Transport Principle 4: Combine reasons to travel with multiple events to be attended in a single or nearby location.

Field work Principle 1: Optimise emissions of the operating platform and the management of resources on board.

Field work Principle 2: Stop pollution of the ocean with technological equipment (e.g. drifters, floats) that is not recuperated post use.

Meetings Principle 1: Where possible, substitute in-person meetings with virtual meetings using video-/ teleconferencing technologies. In addition, all events should have remote participation as an option.

Meetings Principle 2: When organising face to face events, plan multiple events at the same time in the same place to optimise use of time on site and increase impact of events.

Meetings Principle 3: Implement a regional hub approach, for which each hub is reachable by land transport.

Meetings Principle 4: When organising in person events, apply principles for responsible and sustainable events.

DT Principle 1: Implement an Environmental Digital Sustainability approach on all our online platforms for the full Virtual Life Cycle.

DT Principle 2: Practice digital sobriety and minimalist approach in project communication.

Products Principle 1: Consider the sustainability aspects of the full life cycle of materials and products, from the start of supply chain to the disposal/re-entry into cycle stages.

6.2 Proposed timeline for developing and implementing the roadmap

